

isoQUINOLINE DERIVATIVES. PART VI

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As in the case of ethyl α -methyl- α -acetamido- β -phenylpropionate (Part V, this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 425), the corresponding α -ethyl or α -propyl analogue has furnished, when treated with P_2O_5 in an inert solvent, 1-methyl-3-ethyl (or propyl)-*isoquinoline*, the structure of which has been confirmed by an independent synthesis.

In Part V (this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 425) it has been recorded that ethyl α -methyl- α -acylamido- β -phenylpropionate, when subjected to the Bischler-Napieralski cyclisation with phosphorus pentoxide in an inert solvent, yields 1-alkyl-3-methyl*isoquinoline*. This reaction is of interest in that it apparently involves, in one operation, cyclodehydration, decarbonylation and dehydrogenation, and has been found to be realised when the nature of the acylamido group is varied. However, it has been indicated that the presence of a quaternary carbon atom in the above ester might promote this facile reaction, and consequently it has now been considered desirable to ascertain, in this respect, the influence of substituents attached to this quaternary carbon atom. Extension of work along this line might render possible an assessment regarding the general applicability of the reaction.

α -Amino- α -ethyl (or propyl)- β -phenylpropionic acid (I), obtained by alkaline hydrolysis of 5-benzyl-5-ethyl (or propyl)-hydantoin, has been acetylated to furnish (II). The ester (III), obtained from (II), has been subjected to the Bischler-Napieralski cyclisation with phosphorus pentoxide in presence of an inert solvent, when a base, agreeing on analysis with (IV), has been obtained. The structure (IV) has been established by an independent synthesis: Benzylethyl (or propyl) ketone (V) has been converted into the amine (VII) by the Leuckart procedure (cf. Ingersoll *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1808). The intermediate *N*-formyl derivative (VI) has been isolated and hydrolysed to the free base (VII). Although the amine (VII) may be accessible through other routes, previously recorded (Rosenmund *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1942, 75B, 1850; Kornblum and Iffland, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 2137; Pohland and Sullivan, *ibid.*, 1953, 75, 5893; Ishiwata and Suzuki, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1951, 71, 1263), it has been found to be of advantage to apply the Leuckart procedure to obtain the same. The possibility of utilising (VII) for the synthesis of (IV) with such a substitution as ethyl or propyl in 3-position has been tested by subjecting (VI) to the action of a mixture of phosphorus oxychloride and polyphosphoric acid to furnish 3-ethyl (or propyl)-3:4-dihydro*isoquinoline* (VIII). (VIII) has been dehydrogenated over Pd—C to furnish 3-ethyl (or propyl)-*isoquinoline* (IX), previously prepared through different routes (Damerow, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2237; Albahary, *Ber.*, 1896, 29, 2397). Accordingly, (VII) has been acetylated and the acetyl derivative (X), when treated with phosphorus oxychloride in an inert solvent, has furnished 1-methyl-3-ethyl (or propyl)-3:4-dihydro*isoquinoline* (XI). On dehydrogenation over Pd—C, (XI) has readily furnished (IV).

It is, thus, evident that with such a substitution as methyl, ethyl or propyl in the quaternary carbon atom in (III), the fully aromatised isoquinoline derivative (IV) is obtained by the Bischler-Napieralski cyclisation of (III) with phosphorus pentoxide. It is significant to record that in the above conversion of (III: R=Me) to (IV: R=Me) (cf. Part V, *loc. cit.*), carbon monoxide is now found* to be eliminated, as identified by a solution of sodium palladous chloride containing sodium acetate and confirmed by ammoniacal cuprous chloride adsorption. This lends an insight into the mechanism of the above reaction, and although the presence of ethanol could not possibly be detected in the reaction mixture, there is no doubt that the above reaction involves cyclo-dehydration and elimination of carbon monoxide and, consequently, of ethanol (cf. Mannich and Walther, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1927, 265, 1; Rosenmund *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1927, 60, 392). Work, which is now in progress to see if such elimination of carbon monoxide is taking place during the formation of fully aromatised isoquinoline derivatives, when α -methyl- α -acetamido- β -phenylpropionic acid or (α -acetamido- β -phenyl)-ethylmethyl ketone or their analogues are subjected to the Bischler-Napieralski cyclisation (cf. Ghosh and Dutta, *this Journal*, 1955, 32, 17, 755; Ghosh, Bhattacharya and Dutta, *ibid.*, 1958, 36, 758), will form the subject matter for a future communication.

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E X P E R I M E N T A L

α -Amino- α -ethyl- β -phenylpropionic Acid (I: R=Et).—5-Benzyl-5-ethylhydantoin Herbst and Johnson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 2463) (125 g.) was treated with aqueous NaOH solution (30%, 360 c.c.) and refluxed on a wiregauze for 24 hours. The solution was acidified with HCl and the unhydrolysed hydantoin filtered. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness on a steam-bath and the residue extracted with anhydrous ethanol. The ethanolic solution was concentrated and then treated with pyridine, when the amino-acid (23.5 g.) was precipitated. It was crystallised from aqueous ethanol as colorless microcrystalline powder, m.p. 282-83° (decomp.). (Found: N, 7.20. $C_{11}H_{15}O_2N$ requires N, 7.25%). It is readily soluble in aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution and in HCl (dilute).

α -Acetamido- α -ethyl- β -phenylpropionic Acid (II: R=Et).—The above amino-acid (6.72 g.) was mixed with acetic anhydride (5 g.) and pyridine (5 g.) and heated on a steam-bath for 5 hours. Pyridine was removed by steam distillation and the residual solid (7 g.) was crystallised from aqueous ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 208-209°. (Found: N, 5.85. $C_{13}H_{17}O_2N$ requires N, 5.56%).

Ethyl α -Acetamido- α -ethyl- β -phenylpropionate (III: R=Et).—A mixture of (II: R=Et; 27 g.), ethanol (160 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 1.6 c.c.) was heated under reflux on the steam bath for 8 hours. After distilling off the excess of ethanol under reduced pressure, the residue was poured into water and the mixture shaken with ether. The ether solution was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water and finally dried (sodium sulphate). Removal of the ether left a liquid which distilled at 164-65°/2-3 mm to a colorless heavy liquid (22 g.). (Found: N, 5.63. $C_{15}H_{21}O_2N$ requires N, 5.32%). On allowing it to stand, it solidified to furnish a colorless crystalline solid (m.p. 71-72°), which was readily soluble in ordinary organic solvents.

Action of P_2O_5 on (III: R=Et): Formation of 1-Methyl-3-ethylisoquinoline (IV: R=Et).—A mixture of the above ester (III: R=Et; 7 g.), P_2O_5 (28 g.) and anhydrous xylene (140 c.c.) was refluxed, under stirring, in an oil-bath for about 7 hours. Xylene was removed under reduced pressure and the residue treated with ice-water. The aqueous solution was washed with ether, treated with charcoal and filtered. The filtrate, on basification with caustic soda, furnished the base (4.2 g.), distilling at 118-19°/0.5-1 mm to a colorless liquid. (Found: N, 8.43. $C_{12}H_{13}N$ requires N, 8.19%).

The *picrate* was crystallised from ethanol (95%) in yellow needles, m.p. 178-79°. (Found: C, 54.31; H, 4.17; N, 14.31. $C_{12}H_{13}N \cdot C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires C, 54.0; H, 4.0; N, 14.0%).

Preparation of Benzylethyl Ketone (V: R=Et).—Ludlam (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 81, 1189) had prepared this ketone by heating a mixture of calcium propionate and calcium phenylacetate. This method suffers from the main disadvantage in that the reaction mass consists of a mixture of benzylethyl, diethyl and dibenzyl ketones and it is naturally tedious to separate the first ketone in a pure form, the yield of which is rather poor. It has been, however, found advantageous to prepare benzylethyl ketone by hydrolysis of α -propionylphenylacetonitrile and subsequent decarboxylation. This nitrile has been prepared by Levine and Hauser (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 760)

by propionylation of phenylacetonitrile in presence of sodamide. We have, however, prepared this nitrile by adding rapidly a mixture of phenylacetonitrile (78.2 g.) and ethyl propionate (104.7 g.) to a warm solution of sodium (20.4 g.) in anhydrous ethanol (220 c.c.). After refluxing for about 7 hours, the reaction mixture was distilled under reduced pressure to remove ethanol. The residual mass was dissolved in a large volume of water, and the aqueous solution, after being washed with benzene, was acidified with acetic acid to furnish a colorless solid (85 g.), which could be crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) in colorless needles, m.p. 72-73° (Levine and Hauser, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 71-72.5°).

α -Propiounylphenylacetonitrile (85 g.), thus prepared, was refluxed with a mixture of glacial acetic acid (170 c.c.) and HCl (conc., comml., 370 c.c.) for about 30 hours. The cooled mixture was extracted with benzene and the benzene solution was thrice washed with 10% NaOH solution and finally with water. Removal of benzene left a liquid (50 g.) which distilled at 226-27° (Ludlam, *loc. cit.*, records b.p. 227°). (Found C, 81.42; H, 8.32. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{12}O$: C, 81.08; H, 8.11%).

The *semicarbazone* was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 152-53° (Ivanov, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1937, 2, 4, 682, records m.p. 153°).

1-Phenyl-2-formamidobutane (VI: R=Et).—Formic acid (50 g., 98-100%) was neutralised with ammonium carbonate (50 g.) and the water was distilled from the solution till the temperature of the liquid recorded 165°. The solution was cooled to room temperature and benzylethyl ketone (27.8 g.) was added when a layer was formed. The flask was fitted with an upright air condenser which, in its turn, was connected to a downward condenser for distillation and a thermometer was fitted up to the bottom of the flask. The mixture was slowly heated to 180° when water distilled off and then heated at 180-85° for 8 hours. After cooling, the mixture was diluted with water and the oil was extracted with benzene; the benzene solution was dried (sodium sulphate). Removal of benzene left a heavy dark liquid which distilled at 181-82°/2-3 mm to a straw-coloured heavy liquid (28.5 g.). (Found: N, 7.79. $C_{11}H_{15}ON$ requires N, 7.91%).

3-Ethyl-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline (VIII: R=Et).—In a flask, protected from moisture, were added P_2O_5 (111 g.) and orthophosphoric acid (85%, 72 c.c.) and the mixture was heated on a steam-bath for 2 hours under occasional shaking. To the cooled syrupy mass were added (VI: R=Et; 17.5 g.) and $POCl_3$ (22.5 c.c.) and the reaction mixture was heated at 125-30° for 8 hours. The mass was cooled, treated with ice-water and washed with ether. The aqueous solution, on basification with NaOH, liberated the base, which was extracted with ether. Removal of the ether left a mobile red liquid (12 g.) which distilled at 107-108°/1-2 mm to a colorless liquid.

The *picrate* was crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 130-31°. (Found: N, 14.67. $C_{11}H_{11}N$. $C_6H_5O_7N$, requires N, 14.43%).

3-Ethylisoquinoline (IX: R=Et).—A mixture of (VIII: R=Et; 8 g.), tetralin (36 c.c.) and Pd—C (10%, 2.4 g.) was heated at 240-45° for 4 hours in an atmosphere of CO_2 . The mixture was filtered and washed with ether. From the filtrate the base was isolated by extraction with HCl (dilute). The acid solution, on basification with NaOH, furnished the base (6.5 g.) which distilled at 112-13°/1 mm to a colorless liquid.

The *picrate* was crystallised from a large quantity of ethanol in yellow plates, m.p. 174-75° (Damerow, *loc. cit.*, records m.p. 171-72°). (Found: N, 14.62. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{11}N.C_6H_5O_7N_3$: N, 14.51%).

1-Phenyl-2-aminobutane (VII: R=Et).—A mixture of (VI: R=Et: 33.5 g.) and HCl (conc., 22.5 c.c.) was refluxed for 8 hours when it turned dark in colour. The mixture was poured into ice-water and washed with benzene. The aqueous solution, when basified with NaOH, furnished the base which was extracted with benzene. Removal of benzene left a liquid (22.5 g.) which distilled at 117-18°/20-21 mm to a colorless liquid (Kornblum and Ifland, *loc. cit.*, record b.p. 106°/15 mm). (Found: N, 9.39. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{15}N$: N, 9.39%).

The *picrate* was obtained in benzene solution as yellow plates, m.p. 130-31°. (Found: N, 14.58. $C_{10}H_{15}N.C_6H_5O_7N_3$ requires N, 14.81%).

The *benzoyl* derivative was crystallised from aqueous ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 124-25° (Kornblum and Ifland, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 122-22.5°).

1-Phenyl-2-acetamidobutane (X: R=Et).—A mixture of (VII: R=Et; 20.76 g.), acetic anhydride (20 g.) and pyridine (20 g.) was heated on the steam-bath for 5 hours. Pyridine was removed by steam distillation and the residual oil (25 g.), on keeping, gradually solidified. It was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) in colorless needles, m.p. 69-70°. (Found: N, 7.08. $C_{12}H_{17}ON$ requires N, 7.33%).

1-Methyl-3-ethyl-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline (XI: R=Et).—A mixture of (X: R=Et; 10 g.), $POCl_3$ (10 g.) and benzene (100 c.c.) was refluxed for 8 hours, cooled and then poured into ice-water under shaking. The aqueous layer was separated and basified with NaOH. The liberated base was extracted with ether, and removal of the ether left a liquid (5 g.) distilling at 115-16°/1-2 mm to a colorless liquid. (Found: N, 8.34. $C_{12}H_{18}N$ requires N, 8.09%).

The *picrate* was crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 167-68°. (Found: N, 13.68. $C_{12}H_{18}N.C_6H_5O_7N_3$ requires N, 13.93%).

Dehydrogenation of the above base over Pd-C (10%) in presence of tetralin, according to the process described earlier, furnished a base, the *picrate* of which was found identical with that of (IV: R=Et), as confirmed by mixed m.p. and elemental analysis.

5-Benzyl-5-propylhydantoin.—A mixture of benzylpropyl ketone (Ishiwata and Suzuki, *loc. cit.*, 15.5 g.), ammonium carbonate (44.7 g.), potassium cyanide (12.5 g.), ethanol (89.4 c.c.) and water (89.4 c.c.) was heated at 50-60° for 8 hours and then at 70-80° for another 8 hours. The mixture was concentrated and then acidified with HCl. The solid (21.6 g.) was crystallised from ethanol in colorless prisms, m.p. 206-207°. (Found: N, 12.29. $C_{13}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires N, 12.07%).

α -Amino- α -propyl- β -phenylpropionic acid (I: R=Pr) was prepared from the above hydantoin as in the case of (I: R=Et) and was crystallised from aqueous ethanol in colorless clusters of needles m.p. 285-86° (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.48. $C_{13}H_{17}O_2N$ requires N, 6.76%).

α -Acetamido- α -propyl- β -phenylpropionic acid (II: R=Pr) was prepared in the usual way and was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 223-24°. (Found: N, 5.84. $C_{14}H_{19}O_2N$ requires N, 5.62%).

Ethyl α -acetamido- α -propyl- β -phenylpropionate (III: R=Pr) was prepared in the usual way and distilled at $175-76^\circ/4-5$ mm to a thick colorless liquid. (Found: N, 4.68. $C_{18}H_{23}O_3N$ requires N, 5.05%). On keeping it solidified to furnish a colorless crystalline solid (m.p. $63-64^\circ$), readily soluble in ordinary organic solvents.

Action of P_2O_5 on (III: R=Pr): Formation of 1-Methyl-3-propylisoquinoline (IV: R=Pr).—The method of procedure was the same as in the case of (III: R=Et). The base distilled at $120-21^\circ/0.5$ mm to a colorless liquid and was characterised as *picrate*, crystallising from ethanol in yellow prisms, m.p. $144-45^\circ$. (Found: N, 13.68. $C_{13}H_{15}N.C_6H_5O_7N_3$ requires N, 13.53%).

1-Phenyl-2-formamidopentane (VI: R=Pr) was similarly prepared, as in the case of (VI: R=Et), by the action of ammonium formate on benzylpropyl ketone (Ishiwata and Suzuki, *loc. cit.*) and distilled at $178-79^\circ/4-5$ mm to a colorless heavy liquid. (Found: N, 7.17. $C_{12}H_{17}ON$ requires N, 7.33%).

3-Propyl-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline (VIII: R=Pr) was prepared from (VI: R=Pr) by the action of $POCl_3$ and polyphosphoric acid, according to the process described previously, and distilled at $120-21^\circ/4-5$ mm. The *picrate* was crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. $120-21^\circ$. (Found: N, 14.12. $C_{12}H_{15}N.C_6H_5O_7N_3$ requires N, 13.93%).

3-Propylisoquinoline (IX: R=Pr) was prepared from (VIII: R=Pr) by dehydrogenation over Pd-C (10%) in tetralin, according to the process described previously, and was characterised as *picrate*, crystallising from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. $163-64^\circ$ (Albahary, *loc. cit.*, records m.p. 161°). (Found: N, 14.21. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{13}N.C_6H_5O_7N_3$: N, 14.0%).

1-Phenyl-2-aminopentane (VII: R=Pr) was obtained from (VI: R=Pr) by hydrolysis with HCl (conc.) in the usual way and distilled at $104-105^\circ/5-6$ mm (Kornblum and Iffland, *loc. cit.*, record b. p. $118^\circ/15$ mm). (Found: N, 8.89. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{17}N$: N, 8.59%).

The *benzoyl* derivative was crystallised from ethanol in colorless rectangular plates, m.p. $124-25^\circ$ (Kornblum and Iffland, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. $123-123.5^\circ$; Ishiwata and Suzuki, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 120°).

1-Phenyl-2-acetamidopentane (X: R=Pr) was prepared from (VII: R=Pr) in the usual way and was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. $91-92^\circ$. (Found: N, 6.55. $C_{13}H_{19}ON$ requires N, 6.83%).

1-Methyl-3-propyl-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline (XI: R=Pr) was obtained from (X: R=Pr) by treatment with $POCl_3$ in presence of benzene in the usual way and distilled at $103-104^\circ/1-2$ mm to a colorless liquid.

The *picrate* was crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. $152-53^\circ$. (Found: N, 13.56. $C_{13}H_{17}N.C_6H_5O_7N_3$ requires N, 13.46%).

Dehydrogenation, in the usual way, of the above base over Pd-C (10%) in presence of tetralin has furnished a base, the *picrate* of which has been found to be identical with that of (IV: R=Pr), as confirmed by mixed m.p. and elemental analysis.

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